

Performance Management as Correlate of Job Commitment Among Academic Staff in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract:

This study examined the relationship between performance management and job commitment among academic staff in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. The study specifically examined the level of academic staff job commitment. The study further examined the level of performance management in Colleges of Education, Southwest Nigeria. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised all the 2,748 academic staff in public Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for the study was 600 academic staff in public Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling procedure which include simple random, proportionate stratified and purposive sampling techniques were used to select sample for the study. Two sets of instrument tagged "Performance Management Questionnaire (PMQ)" and "Academic Staff Job Commitment Questionnaire (ASJCQ)" were used to collect relevant data for the study. The two instruments were validated by experts. PMQ and ASJCQ had reliability coefficients of 0.88 and 0.82 respectively. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the inferential statistics involving Pearson Product Moment Correlation and multiple regression analysis were used to test the hypotheses. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that the level of academic staff job commitment in colleges of education in Southwest, Nigeria was high. It was also revealed that the level of performance management in colleges of education in Southwest, Nigeria was high. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that National Commission for Colleges of Education should set policies in ensuring specific performance management system to improve academic staff job commitment.

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Introduction

Institutions of higher education have been regarded to have an important role to play in socio-economic change and development taking place in the society. They have a crucial role in helping to build new institutions in a civil society, in encouraging and facilitating new cultural values and in training and socializing members of new social elites. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) in the National Policy on Education articulates the objectives of higher Education to include the contribution to national development through relevant manpower training, the acquisition, development and inculcation of proper values for the development of intellectual capability of individuals to understand and appreciate the local and external environments. The establishment of higher institution is generally predicated on the dire need of producing a high level manpower or personnel to run the economy towards attaining greater growth and development. One of the main administrative tasks of school management is to optimize staff job commitment. It is also deemed pertinent to do everything possible in order to retain good employees, thus, paying lots of attention to employee's job commitment. Moreover, it is important to make sure that employee's performance is in relation to his or her commitment. These aspects are also increasingly important in Colleges of Education.

Job commitment is considered as one of the foremost important goals of any organization in order to maintain its existence and survival. Academic staff with higher degree of commitment toward the educational objectives are perceived to be more productive, harmonious, have better loyalty towards their work, and possess higher responsibility (Karim and Rehman, 2012). Moreover, academic staff with strong commitment are likely to develop emotional attachment to their organisations and feel happy with greater aspirations to make meaningful contributions. Sahoo, Behera and Tripathy (2010) demonstrated that, an academic staff who is committed to his or her job and career has less intention to take leave or quit, tend to feel satisfied about the job, and has higher intrinsic motivation. Job commitment has been widely accepted to be advantageous for both the organisation and its employees as it can reinforce the feelings of belongingness, security of the job, career development, improved compensation, and higher intrinsic rewards (Azeem and Akhtar, 2014).

However, it appears that all is not well with the Colleges of Education in Nigeria today with special reference to Southwest as academic staff who are the main players in the institutions seem not to be committed to their job any longer in the areas of teaching, research and community services. Teaching can be defined as engagement with learners to enable them understand and apply knowledge, concepts and processes to everyday activities. It includes design, content selection, delivery, assessment and reflection. To teach is to engage students in learning, thus, teaching consists of getting students involved in the active construction of knowledge. A teacher requires not only knowledge of subject matter, but knowledge of how students learn and how to transform them into active learners. According to Nilsen and Albertalli (2002), teaching in its broadest sense is the process whereby a teacher guides a learner or group of learners to a higher level of knowledge or skills. Effective teaching, then, require a commitment to systematic understanding of learning. The aim of teaching is not only to transmit information, but also to transform students from passive recipients of other

people's knowledge, to shape students character and behaviour, teachers help students to be strong and independent also to motivate students and help them to be successful in life.

It has been observed that some academic staff in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria showed low commitment to their work in terms of poor punctuality at work while some are in the habits of not covering their course contents, delays in marking of examination scripts and late release of students results are some of the observed indices of low commitment of some academic staff. Some academic staff seem to have developed laissez-faire attitude to teaching, while some are no longer committed to the job, some engage in other services outside their main institutions when they ought to have developed interest in coming up with solutions and ideas that can bring progress to the institutions.

Research is defined as the creation of new knowledge and/or the use of existing knowledge in a new and creative way so as to generate new concepts, methodologies, understanding, inventions and applications of the knowledge. Victoria University (2014) therefore submitted that, research could include synthesis and analysis of previous research to the extent that it leads to new and creative outcomes. The principal criterion for promoting lecturers from one level to the other is the lecturer's productivity defined in terms of research output or publications in referred national and international journals and text books.

In terms of research, some academic staff do not devote much time for depth of good research work. It appears some academic staff are not interested in breaking new grounds in research but only publish for the sake of getting their promotion as and when due. The researcher observed that there is a decline in the level of research being conducted in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. It has been observed over the years that some academic staff seem to have poor attendance in conferences both in and outside their institutions, some academic staff seem not to be committed in participating in conference planning and execution.

Community services are referred to as the services rendered to the society, in which the academic staff function. These may include services to faculties, university, families and even the nation at large. In doing this, the academic staff help to explore the potentials and capabilities of individuals during their professional outreach. Observably, it appears that the level of participation in community services of some academic staff seems to be low and this is because they are not given orientation on how to handle and discharge their duties. Community services of academic staff may be in form of serving as advisory board members or referees to a scholarly journal. It has been observed that, some academic staff seem not to be committed in performing public enlightenment programmes and some academic staff have been observed not to render selfless consultancy services to communities and agencies among others.

The commitment to teaching, research and community services cannot be over-emphasised among academic staff in Colleges of Education. It appears that this non-commitment of academic staff might be as a result of inadequate use of performance management. Performance management has a crucial role in reforming the educational system and increasing commitment of academic staff, as well as raising the overall quality of higher education.

Performance management is a process for establishing shared understanding about what is to be achieved and how it is to be achieved, and an approach to managing and developing people

that improves individual, team and organizational performance (Bjerregaard, 2014). Performance management has been seen as a tool which focuses on managing the individual and work environment in such a manner that an individual or team can achieve set organizational goals (Esu & Inyang, 2009).

Performance management in Colleges of Education is considered as a tool for management of individual performance, and the need is growing drastically (Mellahi, 2016). It has been observed that performance of individuals are sometimes not been calculated rightly resulting in dissatisfaction and creating an underwhelmed environment for the institution. Effective performance management enables employees to contribute effectively and productively to the overall direction and the accomplishment of the organisation's goals and objectives.

Performance management is also a strategic and comprehensive approach to managing people and the workplace culture and environment. Effective performance management enables employees to contribute effectively and committedly to the overall organisation direction and the achievement of the organisation's goals and objectives.

Literature Review

Concept of Performance Management

In the organizational context, performance is usually defined as the extent to which an organizational member contributes to achieving the goals of the organization. Employees are a primary source of competitive advantage in service-oriented organizations (Asamu, 2013). In addition, a commitment performance approach views employees as resources or assets, and values their voice. Employee performance plays an important role for organizational performance. Employee performance is originally what an employee does or does not do. Performance of employees could include; quantity of output, quality of output, timeliness of output, presence at work and cooperativeness (Gungor, 2011). Boachie-Mensah (2011) posited that, improved individual employee performance could improve organizational performance as well. Performance is the measurement of actual output or result against set goals. The line managers and leaders play vital roles by accommodating employees concerns so as to maintain organization performance (Kazimoto, 2016). Performance can be defined as the achievement of specified task measured against predetermined or identified standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed. In an employment contract, performance is deemed to be the accomplishment of a commitment in such a manner that releases the performer from all liabilities laid down under the contract.

Concept of Job Commitment

Organizational commitment is considered as one of the foremost important goals of any organization in order to maintain its existence and survival. According to Karim & Rehman (2012), highly committed and loyal employees are very important in order to achieve organisational goals. This is because employees with higher degree of commitment toward the organization are perceived to be more productive, harmonious, have better loyalty towards their work, and possess higher responsibility and job satisfaction (Karim & Rehman, 2012). Moreover, employees with strong organisational commitment are likely to develop emotional attachment to their organisations and feel happy with greater aspirations to make meaningful contributions. Sahoo, Behera and Tripathy (2010) demonstrated that, an employee who is committed to his or her job and career has less intention to take leave or quit, tend to feel satisfied about the job, and has higher intrinsic motivation.

Purpose of the Study

The study examined performance management as correlate of job commitment among academic staff in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. Specifically, the study investigated:

- i. the level of academic staff job commitment in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria;
- ii. the level of performance management in Colleges of Education;

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. What is the level of academic staff job commitment in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of performance management in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was generated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between performance management and academic staff job commitment in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consisted of all the 2,748 academic staff in public Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 600 academic staff in public Colleges of Education (Federal and State) in the Southwest, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used in the selection of the sample for the study.

In the first stage, four states were selected out of the six states in Southwest, Nigeria using simple random sampling technique. In the second stage, one public College of Education which includes College of Education, Ikere Ekiti from Ekiti State, Federal College of Education from Ogun State, College of Education, Ila-orangun from Osun State and Emmanuel Alayande College of Education from Oyo State through stratified random sampling technique. The third stage involved the use of proportionate random sampling technique to select 600 academic staff from the sampled 4 public Colleges of Education. The fourth stage, 15 departments were selected from the 4 public Colleges of Education earlier selected using simple random sampling technique. In stage five, 10 lecturers were selected in each department of the selected Colleges of Education using simple random sampling technique. The Heads of Departments of the selected academic staff were selected using purposive sampling technique to assess the academic staff job commitment. Two self-designed research instruments tagged "Performance Management Questionnaire (PMQ)" and "Academic Staff Job Commitment Questionnaire (ASJCQ)" were used to collect relevant data for the study. Performance Management Questionnaire was of two sections. Section A of PMQ sought for bio – data of the respondents, section B consisted of 30 items that elicited information on performance management.

Academic Staff Job Commitment Questionnaire was also of three sections. Section A of ASJCQ sought for bio – data of the Head of Departments that assessed the academic staff. Section B sought for the bio-data of the academic staff to be assessed while section C consisted of 20 items that measured job commitment of the academic staff through their effectiveness and efficiency in teaching, research and community service. Face and content validity of the instruments were ensured by experts. The reliability of the instruments “Performance Management Questionnaire (PMQ) and Academic Staff Job Commitment Questionnaire (ASJCQ)” were determined through test-retest method in one college of Education outside the sampled areas. The school shared similar characteristics with the colleges sampled. The instruments were administered on 48 respondents. 40 Academic staffs responded to Performance Management Questionnaire (PMQ) and 8 Heads of Departments responded to Academic Staff Job Commitment Questionnaire (ASJCQ) to assess the 40 Academic staffs) twice within the interval of two weeks. The two sets of responses were correlated and analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis (PPMC). A reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained for PMQ and 0.82 was obtained for ASJCQ. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics such as: frequency counts, percentages, mean, standard deviation and bar chart while Hypotheses 1 was tested using inferential statistics of Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of academic staff job commitment in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of level of academic staff job commitment in Colleges of Education N= 593

Items	Excellent %	Good %	Fair %	Poor %	Mean	SD	Remark
Teaching	305 (51.3)	260 (43.8)	28 (4.7)	- -	3.46	0.58	Agreed
Research	226 (38.1)	333 (56.1)	34 (5.7)	- -	3.32	0.56	Agreed
Community Service	234 (39.4)	345 (58.1)	15 (2.5)	- -	3.37	0.52	Agreed
Mean					3.38		

Table 1 showed the item analysis of academic staff job commitment in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. The result shows that, using a criterion mean score of 2.50 for the rating scale, all the items had mean scores above the cut-off point. This implies that the level of academic staff job commitment in colleges of education in Southwest, Nigeria was high.

Research Question 2: What is the level of performance management in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of the level of performance management in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria

Items	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	Mean	SD	Remark
1. Employee Orientation	43 (7.2)	240 (48.4)	276 (4.64)	35 (5.9)	2.49	0.68	Disagreed
2. Employee Appraisal	88 (14.8)	318 (53.5)	164 (27.6)	24 (4.0)	2.79	0.68	Agreed
3. Feedback	13 (2.2)	343 (57.7)	160 (26.9)	78 (13.1)	2.49	0.7	Disagreed
4. Team Work	47 (7.9)	442 (74.4)	98 (16.5)	7 (1.2)	2.89	0.49	Agreed
5. Goal Setting	70 (11.8)	312 (52.5)	173 (29.1)	939 (6.6)	2.70	0.72	Agreed
6. Compensation	53 (8.9)	180 (30.3)	283 (47.6)	78 (13.1)	2.35	0.78	Disagreed
Total						2.62	

Table 2 showed the item analysis of performance management technique used in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. The result shows that, using a criterion mean score of 2.50 for the rating scale; all the items had mean score above the cut-off point. This implies that the level of performance management in colleges in southwest, Nigeria was high.

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between performance management and academic staff job commitment in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria

In testing this hypothesis, data on performance management were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of PMQ (item 1-30) in the questionnaire. Data on academic staff job commitment were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of ASJCQ (item 1-20) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 3.

Table 3: Relationship between performance management and academic staff job commitment

Variables	N	Mean	Standard Dev	r-cal	P-value
Performance Management	594	78.50	5.20		

0.612* 0.000

Academic Staff Job Commitment	594	67.73	3.97
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*P<0.05

Table 3 showed that the r-cal value of 0.612 is significant at 0.05 level of significance because the P-value (0.000) < 0.05. The null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between performance management and academic staff job commitment.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that the level of academic staff job commitment in colleges of education in Southwest, Nigeria was high. The findings of the study also revealed that the level of performance management in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria was high. The study further revealed that there was significant relationship between performance management and academic staff job commitment in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. The probable reason could be due to the processes of performance management. In support of this finding, Idemobi and Onyeizugbe (2011) revealed that performance review techniques have significant effect on employees' commitment and productivity. Ngige (2015) revealed that, the performance management factors in the selected organizations had positive influence on employee productivity. The implication of this finding is that well implemented performance management will boost the morale of employees and increase commitment.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that performance management in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria was high. It was also concluded that job commitment among academic staff in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria was high. The study further revealed that there was significant relationship between performance management and academic staff job commitment in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that National Commission of Colleges Education should set policies in ensuring specific performance management system to improved academic staff job commitment.

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